

Priming Effects of Kilohertz-Frequency Pulse Train on Cortical Neural Excitability in Mouse Brain Slices

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Abstract: Recently, kilohertz-frequency pulse-train stimulation has attracted attention as a novel neuromodulation method, as an alternative to conventional electrical pulses delivered at repetition rates below 200 Hz. In this study, we propose a new stimulation paradigm in which kilohertz-frequency stimulation is applied not as the main stimulus that directly induces neuronal excitation, but as a priming stimulus applied prior to the main stimulus. Using physiological experiments and numerical simulations, we demonstrated that the cortical response to the main stimulus was partially suppressed by the priming stimulus. These findings suggest the potential of kilohertz-frequency stimulation as a new strategy for precise activation of neural circuits in cortical prostheses.

Keywords: Intracortical Neural prosthesis, Kilohertz-Frequency Microstimulation, Physiological Experiment, Biophysical Simulation, Neural Excitability

I. INTRODUCTION

Intracortical visual prostheses, which evoke artificial light percepts (phosphenes) by electrically stimulating the visual cortex, have emerged as a promising approach for vision restoration in individuals with acquired blindness[1][2]. However, intracortical electrical stimulation non-selectively excites neuronal structures in the vicinity of the electrode, limiting control over phosphene location, shape, and brightness. In addition to somata and axon initial segments (AIS), it can also stimulate passing axons and diverse neuronal types, resulting in complex and often unpredictable neural responses [3]. To address these limitations, several strategies have been proposed, including stimulus waveform optimization[4][5][6] or current steering with the use of multielectrode arrays[2][7][8]. While these methods have improved spatial resolution to some extent, precise control of neuronal activity via microstimulation still remains challenging, leading to novel approaches that go beyond conventional stimulation paradigms.

In this context, “kilohertz-frequency stimulation” has attracted increasing interest as a neuromodulation method with distinct physiological effects. For example, Ravasio et al. (2025) demonstrated that 1-kHz pulse train stimulation in awake mice elicited brain-region-specific responses, with balanced excitation–inhibition in the cortex and predominantly inhibitory activity in the hippocampus[9]. Other studies have reported

conduction block, desynchronization, and selective suppression of neural excitability in response to kilohertz-frequency stimulation[10]. These findings suggest that kilohertz-frequency pulse train engages neural circuits through mechanisms that differ fundamentally from those of conventional low-frequency stimulation.

Motivated by these observations, we investigated whether kilohertz-frequency stimulation could be repurposed as a priming paradigm—specifically, by applying a brief sequence of subthreshold current pulses prior to a conventional stimulus, in order to transiently modulate cortical excitability with fine temporal control. In this study, we examined this concept using acute brain slice preparations from mice. Subthreshold current pulses were delivered to layer IV or layer II/III of the primary visual cortex (V1) with and without a kilohertz-frequency priming stimulus.

Voltage-sensitive dye (VSD) imaging [11] revealed that the priming stimulus attenuates the subsequent neural response in the vicinity of the stimulation site. To complement the experimental observations, we also conducted numerical simulations using biophysically detailed models of cortical neurons. By comparing neural responses with and without priming stimulation, we aimed to characterize how high-frequency subthreshold input alters subsequent stimulus responsiveness. Our findings offer insights into the mechanism of kilohertz-based neuromodulation and

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suggest its potential utility for improving spatial resolution and selectivity in cortical visual prostheses.

II. METHODS

A. Physiology

All animal experiments were approved by the Animal Experiment Committee of Mie University and conducted in accordance with international guidelines[12][13].The tissue preparation, experimental procedures, and data analyses were performed as described in our previous studies[11][14]. Briefly, brains were extracted from C57BL/6 mice ($n = 12$, female, 3–5 weeks old) and sectioned coronally into 300- μm slices containing V1. Each slice was stained with VSD, “NK3630”, transferred to a recording chamber, and continuously perfused with oxygenated artificial cerebrospinal fluid (aCSF) ($\sim\text{pH}$ 7.4, aerated with 95% O_2 and 5% CO_2). As shown in Fig. 1, VSD imaging was performed over a $154 \times 820\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ field either covering from layers II/III to VI along the dorso-ventral axis (A) or locating within layer II/III along the medio-lateral axis (B) of V1, by acquiring images with a resolution of 12×64 binned pixels at 1000 frames per second using an Electron Multiplying Charge-Coupled Device camera.

The acquired imaging data were processed and analyzed in MATLAB (ver. R2022b). The relative change in transmitted light intensity due to membrane voltage-related absorbance changes of VSD was calculated as $\Delta T/T_0$, where T_0 denotes the baseline

transmission intensity and ΔT represents the change from this baseline at each time point. Images acquired with no electrical stimulus were subtracted from images acquired with a stimulus, and the resulting images were averaged across 200 repetitions. To further improve the signal-to-noise ratio, the processed images were filtered offline using a spatial Gaussian filtering (5×5 -pixel mask; $\sigma \approx 1.11$ pixels). The final $\Delta T/T_0$ value was used to estimate normalized membrane potential changes and expressed in arbitrary units (a.u.), which was color-coded in the time series images of $\Delta T/T_0$ (see Fig. 5A).

Electrical stimulation was delivered through the tip of a glass micropipette electrode (1-2 $\text{M}\Omega$, tip diameter $\sim 6 \mu\text{m}$) inserted into either layer IV ($n = 6$) or II/III ($n = 6$) at a depth of 0.1-0.15 mm from the cut surface, as described previously [11]. In the present experiment, we used three different patterns of current pulses, as shown in Fig. 1C: (a) main pulse only, (b) main pulse with priming pulses, and (c) priming pulses only. Fig. 1C-a shows recorded traces of the first pattern, consisting of a single cathode-first biphasic current pulse (10 or 20 $\mu\text{A}/\text{phase}$, 0.2 ms/phase). Fig. 1 C-b shows the second pattern, consisting of six subthreshold biphasic pulses (4 $\mu\text{A}/\text{phase}$, 0.2 ms/phase) delivered at 2 kHz prior to the main pulse. Fig. 1 C-c shows the third pattern, consisting only of priming pulses. Each stimulus was repeated 200 times in total (for data averaging; see above) with 10-s intervals, and the same stimulus was not applied in immediate succession.

B. Modeling

Figure 1 Slice preparations and three patterns of current-pulse stimuli

Figure 2 Electrical circuit model of a cortical neuron with the extracellular mechanism

Figure 3 Spatial summation model for approximating the population-level VSD response.

To complement the experimental observations, we conducted numerical simulations using biophysically detailed neuron models implemented in the NEURON simulator[15]. The neuron models were based on quantitative data from the somatosensory cortex of juvenile rats, and were made available by the Blue Brain Project[16][17]. Based on the data from recent connectomic analyses of the mouse V1[18][19], it is estimated that the proportions of excitatory to inhibitory neurons in layer IV are approximately 94 : 6 % in terms of cell number and 89 : 11 % in terms of cell density. Among the excitatory neurons in layer IV of V1, pyramidal neurons account for more than 99% of the

population, whereas spiny stellate neurons comprise less than 1 % [20]. Therefore, we employed a pyramidal-cell model (code: “L4_PC_cADpyr230_3”) from the model database. In addition, we also employed a large-basket-cell (LBC) model (code: “L4_LBC_cSTUT189_5”) from the database, since the majority of inhibitory neurons in layer IV of V1 is LBC type which accounts for approximately 38 % of the population of inhibitory neurons [20].

As illustrated in Fig. 2, each biophysically detailed neuron model was represented as a combination of cable-like compartments, with each compartment further subdivided into multiple segments. Extracellular

current stimulation was implemented by employing NEURON’s built-in extracellular mechanism. This enabled calculation of the extracellular potential and, consequently, the membrane voltage changes ($e_{extra}(i)$ and $V_m(i)$), respectively, in Fig. 2) at every segment in response to current stimuli delivered from a point-source electrode, with a reference electrode assumed at infinity. The parameter values for the extracellular mechanism were set to $xr_{axial} = 10^9 \text{ M}\Omega/\text{cm}$, $xg = 10^9 \text{ S}/\text{cm}^2$, and $C_{extra} = 0 \text{ }\mu\text{F}/\text{cm}^2$, with an extracellular resistivity of $\rho_{extra} = 3312 \text{ }\Omega\text{-cm}$. In addition, we introduced a propagation time constant (200 μs) into the current-pulse waveforms to incorporate the tissue time constant. All simulations were run with a fixed time step of 0.1 μs and temperature of 30 degrees Celsius. Details of the algorithms and code implementation are provided in the official NEURON documentations [15].

To enable comparisons with physiological observations, model-derived VSD responses were calculated from the membrane voltage data obtained in the simulations. First, the response of each segment—that is, the membrane voltage change induced by the stimulus current—was simulated using the model described above. Second, the VSD signal of a neuron-level was defined as a sum of the membrane voltage responses across all segments of the compartments within 0.1 mm from the soma. Such simulated neuron-level VSD responses were obtained through simulations with setting 15 electrode-soma distances of 10 to 150 μm at a 10- μm step. Third, to approximate the population-level VSD response around the two-dimensional x - y coordinate of electrode tip on the imaging frame, we summated the calculated neural-level VSD responses along the z -axis on which the electrode tip was positioned (Fig. 3). This three-step approximation from the simulated voltage responses in neuronal segments to the population-level VSD responses is illustrated in Figure 4, presenting the corresponding response waveforms at each stage. The figure consists of three panels arranged from *left to right*. The first panel shows the membrane voltage response in a single neuronal segment as an example. The middle panel displays the single-neuron VSD

response. The final panel shows the overall population-level VSD response. This final response signal was used for analysis in this study.

III. RESULTS

A. Cortical VSD Responses to the Three Different Stimulation

Fig.5A shows the time-series images of $\Delta T/T_0$ in response to the three patterns of current-pulse stimuli applied to layer IV, averaged across 6 slices. Red arrowheads indicate the approximate position of the stimulating electrode tip. Membrane depolarization was initiated near the electrode tip in layer IV within a few milliseconds after the onset of the main pulse. This immediate response reflects a population action potential directly elicited by the main current pulse [11]. Subsequently, the depolarization in layer IV gradually decayed in amplitude, while membrane depolarization propagated to layer II/III via trans-synaptic excitation[11]. In both layers, the response amplitudes were smaller when the priming pulses were applied (subpanels *b* and *d*) than when no priming was applied (*a* and *c*). As shown in (*e*), the priming pulses alone elicited not transient but gradual depolarizations with relatively small amplitudes in layers IV and II/III, and these depolarizations lasted for a few tens of milliseconds, primarily in layer II/III. This suggests the possibility of incoherent (i.e., desynchronized) firing of action potentials in neuronal axons projecting onto neurons in layer II/III, in response to the priming pulses.

Fig. 5B displays the time courses of spatially integrated $\Delta T/T_0$ signals in a region approximately $38 \times 38 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ in size (3×3 pixels) around the electrode tip. Each of the traces shows the mean (*solid* line) and standard error of the mean (*shaded* area) across the six slices. To compare the depolarizations elicited by the main pulse with and without priming, the response time course obtained with the priming pulses alone (*green dotted* lines, “priming-only”) was subtracted from that obtained with the main pulse plus priming (*red dotted*

Figure 4 Three step approximation from voltage responses in neuronal segments to VSD responses

lines, “w/ priming”), yielding an estimate of the response component attributable to the main pulse in the priming condition (*red solid* lines, “w/ priming minus priming-only”). As shown in the figure, the main pulse-elicited depolarization at 1-2 ms and 2-3 ms after pulse onset (indicated by *blue* and *red circles* in Fig. 5B) was significantly smaller in amplitude with priming (*red solid* line) than without priming (*blue* line, “w/o priming”) (Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $p \sim 0.031$, $n = 6$).

The response difference was likely due to a reduction in action potential firing, as our previous experiments demonstrated that the population action potential directly elicited by a suprathreshold current pulse reaches its peak amplitude at 1-2 ms after pulse onset, while almost no postsynaptic potential is evoked around this time point [11]. This reduction may have further attenuated the subsequent trans-synaptic excitations. The degree of response attenuation is relatively greater

Figure 5 VSD imaging of neural excitations in response to the three patterns of current-pulse stimuli

with the 10- μ A pulse (*upper panel of Fig. 5B*) than with the 20- μ A pulse (*lower panel*).

Similar results were obtained in six additional slices in which the current-pulse stimuli were delivered into layer II/III (*data not shown*). Specifically, the amplitude of the main pulse-elicited depolarization at 1-2 or 2-3 msec after pulse onset was significantly smaller with priming than without priming (Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $p \sim 0.031$, $n = 6$). Moreover, the degree of attenuation was comparable to that observed with the stimulation in layer IV, i.e., $\sim 50\%$ for the 10- μ A pulse and $\sim 20\%$ for the 20- μ A pulse, when measured 1-2 ms after pulse onset.

These physiological observations suggested that the priming pulses reduce action potential firing elicited by the main pulse through a common mechanism, regardless of differences in neuronal structures between layer IV and layer II/III [18][19].

B. Model Responses to the Three Different Stimulation

One of the most relevant mechanisms that could account for the experimental findings in both layers is intrinsic membrane properties commonly expressed across neuron types—such as the voltage-gated Na^+ channels. To test this hypothesis, we next examined the effects of priming in biophysical simulations, in which the neuron model incorporated membrane conductances but excluded synaptic transmission. Because layer IV of V1 is predominated by pyramidal neurons ($\sim 90\%$), we

used the model of this neuron type (see Methods).

Fig. 6A shows the model-derived, population-level VSD responses obtained from the simulations. As examples, the figure illustrates the results when the main pulse amplitude was set to 10 $\mu\text{A}/\text{phase}$ and the priming pulse amplitude was set to either 2 or 4 $\mu\text{A}/\text{phase}$. The simulations captured the essential features of physiological experiments: the response amplitude was significantly smaller with priming (*red trace*) than without priming (*blue trace*). Moreover, the reduction in response amplitude depended on the priming pulse amplitude, with larger priming pulses producing greater attenuation. Although some quantitative differences from the experimental results remained—particularly in the exact amplitude ratios and the time course of response decay—these differences were likely due to the lack of synaptic mechanisms in the model and were outside the scope of the present simulations.

To further investigate the mechanism underlying the priming effects, we analyzed the inactivation variable of the Na^+ channel model inserted in the soma and AIS compartments. As shown in Fig. 6B, the inactivation variable decreased slightly during the course of the priming pulses (*red trace*). As shown in the panel A, the priming pulses caused membrane depolarization (*red trace*, Fig. 6A; *upper inset*, Fig. 6B). In addition, in the Na^+ -channel state transitions, the rate of entry into inactivation is slightly faster than the rate of recovery from inactivation at these membrane potentials (*lower inset*, Fig. 6B). These two factors together resulted in a

Figure 6 Model-derived, population-level VSD signal and Na^+ -channel inactivation variable in response to the stimuli

decrease in the inactivation variable during the course of the priming pulses, thereby suppressing action potential firing.

We also employed the LBC model to represent an inhibitory neuron type (see Methods). When the main pulse amplitude was set to 10 $\mu\text{A}/\text{phase}$, the model-derived, population-level VSD signals from this neuron type exhibited a depolarizing response only when the soma/AIS was located within 20 μm from the electrode tip. In cells located close to the electrode tip, the main pulse-elicited VSD response was attenuated with 8- μA priming pulses but only slightly with 4- μA priming pulses. Moreover, because the density of inhibitory neurons in layer IV of V1 is significantly lower than that of excitatory neurons (<10 %) [18][19], the likelihood that such responses contributed to the VSD signal shown in Fig. 5B is considered negligible. Taken together, these results suggest that the priming effect observed in the experiments is mediated primarily by excitatory neurons and only minimally by inhibitory neurons.

These simulation results were consistent with the physiological observations showing that the priming pulses reduce the main pulse-elicited response, at least in part, by altering intrinsic membrane excitability. Specifically, the partial inactivation of Na^+ channels in excitatory neurons provided a plausible explanation for the VSD response attenuation observed in the experiments.

IV. DISCUSSION

In this study, we examined the potential application of a kilohertz-frequency current-pulse train as a priming paradigm, based on both physiological experiments (Fig. 5) and biophysical simulations (Fig. 6).

In the experiments, the priming pulses attenuated the subsequent membrane excitation elicited by the main current pulse. Because this involved a reduction in response amplitude within a few milliseconds after the onset of the main pulse, the priming pulses were considered, at least in part, to alter the intrinsic membrane excitability of neuron and thereby inhibit action potential firings in response to the main pulse. This was consistent with our preliminary experiments, in which the priming also attenuated main pulse-elicited depolarizations even under low- Ca^{2+} conditions that suppress synaptic transmissions in V1 (*data not shown*).

In accordance with these experimental observations, the simulations indicated that the intrinsic membrane excitability of neurons was altered by the priming. Specifically, repetitive subthreshold-level membrane

depolarizations during the priming-pulse train induced partial inactivation of voltage-gated Na^+ channels, thereby attenuating neuronal responsiveness mediated by Na^+ -dependent action potential firing.

Despite this agreement between experiments and simulations, the present model only explains the initial action potential responses elicited by the main pulse. Because the simulations in this study aimed primarily to elucidate the contribution of intrinsic membrane properties to the priming effect, and focused specifically on Na^+ -dependent excitability, synaptic components of the response were not quantitatively reproduced. In future work, extending the model to incorporate synaptic mechanisms and network-level interactions will be essential for quantitatively reproducing the full range of physiological responses. In addition, extracellular transfer impedance, which includes both resistive and capacitive components, needs to be considered for computing extracellular potential changes in response to current stimuli. Once these factors are incorporated into the simulation model, it is expected to quantitatively reproduce the physiological observations. The present study provides an essential foundation for such future work. Moreover, the findings also suggest that kilohertz-frequency priming could serve as a novel strategy to enhance the selectivity of intracortical microstimulation. Before translation to clinical applications, however, its effectiveness should be further validated in *in-vivo* animal models, which will be a critical step toward the development of more effective cortical visual prostheses.

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